

Application of Additive Manufacturing in Prosthodontics: Rehabilitation of a Missing Central Incisor Using an SLM Printed Maryland Bridge - A Clinical Case Report

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Abstract

Replacement of missing anterior teeth in adolescent patients presents a significant challenge in Prosthodontics due to aesthetic demands, psychological impact, and limitations associated with definitive treatment modalities during active craniofacial growth. Implant supported prostheses are generally contraindicated until skeletal maturity is achieved, thereby necessitating conservative interim treatment alternatives. Maryland bridges have emerged as a minimally invasive treatment option because they preserve maximum tooth structure while restoring aesthetics and function. Recent advancements in digital dentistry and additive manufacturing technologies such as CAD-CAM and selective laser melting (SLM) have further enhanced the precision and predictability of fixed prosthodontic rehabilitation. A 14-year old female patient reported with a chief complaint of a missing maxillary right central incisor. Clinical and radiographic examination revealed teeth 12 and 21 with adequate periodontal support, which were selected as abutments for Maryland bridge. Conservative palatal tooth preparation was performed followed by elastomeric impression making using putty and light body polyvinyl siloxane impression material. The definitive cast was poured in die stone and digitized using a laboratory scanner. The prosthetic framework was designed using CAD-CAM software and fabricated in cobalt chromium alloy through additive manufacturing using selective laser melting technology. The SLM fabricated Maryland bridge demonstrated satisfactory marginal adaptation, passive fit, aesthetics, and functional stability with favorable patient acceptance. Integration of digital workflow with additive manufacturing improved prosthesis precision, reduced laboratory inaccuracies, and enhanced overall treatment predictability.

Keywords: Maryland bridge, additive manufacturing, selective laser melting, CAD-CAM, digital prosthodontics.

Introduction

Restoration of missing anterior teeth remains one of the most challenging procedures in Prosthodontics because the anterior dentition plays a vital role in aesthetics, phonetics, mastication, and psychosocial well being. Loss of an anterior tooth during adolescence can significantly affect facial appearance, confidence, speech, and social interaction, thereby negatively influencing the overall quality of life of the patient.¹ Rehabilitation of such cases requires careful treatment planning with emphasis on aesthetics, preservation of tooth structure, function, and long-term prognosis. Conventional fixed dental prostheses require extensive preparation of adjacent teeth, which may result in unnecessary removal of healthy enamel and dentin with possible compromise of pulpal vitality.² Similarly, implant supported prostheses, although considered an ideal definitive treatment option, are generally contraindicated in adolescent

patients due to ongoing craniofacial growth, which may lead to infra-occlusion and aesthetic discrepancies over time.³ Therefore, minimally invasive treatment approaches are preferred in younger patients. Resin bonded fixed dental prostheses, commonly known as Maryland bridges, were developed as conservative alternatives for replacement of missing teeth while preserving maximum enamel structure of the abutment teeth. These prostheses utilize metal or ceramic retainers bonded to the lingual surfaces of adjacent teeth, thereby minimizing tooth preparation and preserving natural tooth integrity.⁴ Maryland bridges offer several advantages including satisfactory aesthetics, improved patient comfort, reduced chairside time, reversibility, and economical rehabilitation.⁵

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They are particularly beneficial in adolescent patients where definitive implant therapy must be delayed until completion of skeletal growth. Recent advancements in digital dentistry, CAD-CAM technology, and additive manufacturing techniques such as selective laser melting (SLM) have significantly improved the precision and predictability of prosthesis fabrication.⁶ Digital workflow has minimized human errors and improved reproducibility, precision, and efficiency compared with conventional laboratory procedures.⁷ Selective laser melting is an additive manufacturing process in which cobalt chromium alloy powder is fused layer by layer using a high energy laser beam according to CAD data. SLM-fabricated restorations demonstrate superior marginal adaptation, improved structural homogeneity, reduced porosity, and enhanced mechanical properties compared with conventional cast restorations, thereby improving the overall clinical outcome and longevity of the prosthesis.⁸

Case Report

A 14-year old female patient reported to the Department of Prosthodontics and Crown & Bridge with the chief complaint of missing upper front tooth associated with reduced confidence while smiling and speaking. Clinical examination revealed absence of tooth number 11. Adjacent teeth 12 and 21 were clinically stable with adequate periodontal support and satisfactory oral hygiene. Considering the patient's age, ongoing skeletal growth, and the need for a conservative interim treatment option, a Maryland bridge with bilateral retainers was selected.

Figure 1: Pre-operative photographs

Clinical Procedure

Minimal palatal tooth preparation was carried out on teeth 12 and 21 to receive the retainers of the Maryland bridge. Preparation design included palatal reduction, supragingival finish lines, proximal extension for improved retention, and establishment of a common path of insertion. Final impressions were made using a two-stage putty wash technique with addition silicone impression material (Putty and Light Body, Zhermack). The definitive cast was poured using Type IV die stone to obtain an accurate and dimensionally stable master cast.

Figure 2: Tooth preparation w.r.t. 12 & 21

Digital Workflow

The definitive cast was scanned using a laboratory scanner to obtain a three dimensional digital model. The framework was digitally designed using CAD-CAM software with emphasis on passive fit, connector dimensions, pontic morphology, and stress distribution.

Figure 3: CAD-CAM Design of Maryland Bridge Framework w.r.t. 12,11, 21 Using Exocad Software

Additive Manufacturing using SLM Technology

The Maryland bridge framework was fabricated using cobalt chromium alloy through selective laser melting (SLM) technology. In this additive manufacturing process, thin layers of Co-Cr alloy powder are selectively fused by a high-energy laser according to CAD data in a controlled inert gas environment. Co-Cr alloys are widely used in fixed prosthodontics because of their excellent mechanical strength, corrosion resistance, rigidity, wear resistance, and biocompatibility. Compared with conventional casting procedures, SLM technology provides superior marginal adaptation, improved structural homogeneity, reduced porosity and distortion, enhanced mechanical properties, and better reproducibility, resulting in excellent clinical fit and adaptation of the framework.

Shade selection and ceramic layering

Shade selection was performed before tooth dehydration under natural daylight using the VITA 3D-MASTER shade guide by evaluating value, chroma, and hue to achieve optimal integration with the adjacent dentition. Following successful metal try-in, ceramic veneering of the Maryland bridge was carried out using a feldspathic ceramic system compatible with cobalt-chromium substructures. The procedure included opaque application, dentin and enamel layering, characterization, contouring, and final glazing to reproduce natural aesthetics, translucency, and surface smoothness.

Figure 4: (a) SLM Printed Maryland Bridge Framework w.r.t. 12,11, 21 (b) Metal Try-in w.r.t. 12,11, 21

Figure 6: Post-operative Resin bonded Maryland bridge w.r.t. 12, 11, 21 (Panavia V5 dual cure resin cement)

Figure 7: Extraoral final

Discussion

Replacement of missing anterior teeth in adolescent patients presents significant restorative and psychological challenges because treatment planning must consider aesthetics, phonetics, function, preservation of tooth structure, and ongoing craniofacial growth. Loss of a maxillary central incisor at an early age may adversely affect social confidence and emotional well being, thereby necessitating timely rehabilitation.⁹ Conventional fixed dental prostheses, although mechanically reliable, require aggressive tooth preparation that may compromise healthy enamel and pulpal vitality of adjacent teeth. Such invasive procedures are generally avoided in younger patients whenever possible.¹⁰ Implant-supported restorations are considered the gold standard for replacement of missing teeth in adults; however, implant placement is contraindicated during active skeletal growth because continued eruption of adjacent teeth and alveolar development may result in infraocclusion and compromised aesthetics.¹¹ Resin bonded fixed dental prostheses such as Maryland bridges provide a conservative alternative for interim anterior tooth replacement. These prostheses preserve maximum tooth structure because preparation is usually confined to enamel, thereby enhancing adhesive bonding and minimizing biological damage to abutment teeth.¹² In the present case, bilateral retainers were used to improve retention, resistance, and stress distribution across the prosthesis. The incorporation of CAD-CAM technology significantly enhanced the accuracy and predictability of prosthesis fabrication. Digital impressions and CAD designing enabled precise visualization of framework thickness, connector dimensions, pontic morphology, and path of insertion prior to manufacturing. This digital workflow reduces human errors associated with conventional waxing and casting techniques while improving reproducibility and laboratory efficiency.¹² Selective laser melting technology represents a major advancement in additive manufacturing within Prosthodontics. Unlike conventional lost wax casting procedures, SLM fabricates prosthetic frameworks through controlled layer by layer laser fusion of metal powder based on CAD data. This technique minimizes casting shrinkage, porosity, and distortion while improving structural homogeneity and marginal adaptation. Cobalt-chromium alloys fabricated using SLM demonstrate superior mechanical properties, including high flexural strength, improved rigidity, and excellent corrosion resistance. These characteristics are particularly advantageous for Maryland bridge frameworks because reduced framework thickness can be maintained without compromising structural durability. Furthermore, improved precision of fit contributes to better retention, reduced cement dissolution, and enhanced longevity of the prosthesis.¹³ The ceramic veneering procedure further enhanced the aesthetic outcome by reproducing

translucency, surface texture, and shade characteristics comparable to adjacent natural teeth.⁴ The present clinical report demonstrates that integration of adhesive prosthodontic principles with digital workflow and additive manufacturing technologies can provide a highly conservative, aesthetic, and clinically predictable treatment option for adolescent patients requiring interim anterior tooth replacement. Although long-term follow-up studies are still required to evaluate survival rates of SLM fabricated Maryland bridges, current evidence suggests favorable clinical performance and promising future applications in digitally driven Prosthodontics.

Conclusion

Digitally designed and SLM printed Maryland bridges provide a minimally invasive, aesthetic, and clinically predictable treatment option for interim replacement of missing anterior teeth in adolescent patients. Integration of CAD-CAM workflow with additive manufacturing improves framework precision, adaptation, and treatment predictability while preserving maximum tooth structure.

References

1. Prathyusha P, Jyoti S, Kaul RB, Sethi N. Maryland Bridge: An interim prosthesis for tooth replacement in adolescents. *Int J Clin Pediatr Dent.* 2011; 4 (2): 135-138.
2. Rosenstiel SF, Land MF, Fujimoto J. *Contemporary Fixed Prosthodontics.* 5th ed. St. Louis: Mosby Elsevier; 2015.
3. Livaditis GJ, Thompson VP. Etched castings: An improved retentive mechanism for resin-bonded retainers. *J Prosthet Dent.* 1982; 47 (1): 52-58.
4. Ghimire P, Suwal P, Parajuli PK, Limbu IK, Basnet BB. Maryland bridge as a minimally invasive restoration of a missing anterior tooth. *J Nepal Dent Assoc.* 2021; 21(33):141-144.
5. Van Noort R. The future of dental devices is digital. *Dent Mater.* 2012; 28 (1): 3-12.
6. Alharbi N, Wismeijer D, Osman RB. Additive manufacturing techniques in prosthodontics: Where do we currently stand? *Int J Prosthodont.* 2017; 30 (5): 474-484.
7. Burns DR, Beck DA, Nelson SK. A review of selected dental literature on contemporary provisional fixed prosthodontic treatment. *J Prosthet Dent.* 2003; 90 (5): 474-497.
8. Durey KA, Nixon PJ, Robinson S, Chan MFY. Resin bonded bridges: Techniques for success. *Br Dent J.* 2011; 211 (3): 113-118.
9. Abduo J, Lyons K, Bennamoun M. Trends in computer aided manufacturing in prosthodontics: A review of the available streams. *Int J Dent.* 2014; 2014:783948.
10. Alharbi N, Wismeijer D, Osman RB. Additive manufacturing techniques in prosthodontics: Where do we currently stand? *Int J Prosthodont.* 2017; 30 (5): 474-484.
11. Takaichi A, Suyalatu, Nakamoto T, et al. Microstructures and mechanical properties of Co-Cr-Mo alloys fabricated by selective laser melting. *J Mech Behav Biomed Mater.* 2013; 21: 67-76.
12. Örtorp A, Jönsson D, Mouhsen A, Vult von Steyern P. The fit of cobalt chromium three unit fixed dental prostheses fabricated with four different techniques: A comparative in vitro study. *Dent Mater.* 2011; 27 (4): 356-363.
13. Miyazaki T, Hotta Y, Kunii J, Kuriyama S, Tamaki Y. A review of dental CAD/CAM: Current status and future perspectives. *J Prosthodont Res.* 2009; 53 (1): 1-9.